

INFLUENCE OF TEMPERAMENT TYPES ON EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY

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Abstract: Currently, the study of the influence of temperament types on educational effectiveness is a relevant topic. The role of temperament is important in the development and manifestations of the intellectual potential of each person. This article shows the priority directions of education based on the individual psychological characteristics of the student..

Key words: *Education, efficiency, talent, ability, temperament, junior school age, social environment, psychologist, logical thinking.*

Introduction: Since the first days of independence, serious attention has been paid to solving the problems of national spirituality, national education and training in order to implement the idea of perfect generation.

Nowadays, the demand for the training of highly skilled specialists is increasing day by day. As long as this is the case, there is a need to develop the creative potential of all workers as much as possible, not only of talented individuals. In such conditions, the increasing role of sciences related to human and intellectual potential shows the need to use the hidden possibilities of every human being and to theoretically develop guidelines for their realization.

Literature analysis and methodology

One of the problems that plagues psychologists today is to study the influence of temperament types on cognitive processes in groups of students, to

identify and eliminate factors that have a negative effect on educational effectiveness.

When it comes to the individual characteristics of a person, special attention is paid to their inborn, biological characteristics. Because in fact, on the one hand, a person is a social being, on the other hand, he is also a biological integrity, a substrate that takes on innate qualities - an individual. Temperament and abilities include the qualities that ensure the process of dynamic - changing mental activity of an individual. The importance of these qualities is that they are the basis for other characteristics that are formed later in the process of ontogenetic development. The peculiarity of the qualities related to human temperament is that they ensure the flexibility and dynamics of reactions when a person changes from one type of activity to another, from one emotional state to another, and replaces one skill with another.

The unique characteristics of temperament are felt in training and work. In order to implement an individual, psychologically based approach in the process of education, it is necessary to correctly imagine and know their temperament characteristics. After knowing the conditions of the student's development, it is possible to compare the information about his behavior and activities in different situations, and distinguish random behavior, habits, and the main signs of temperament.

In order to include the student in a certain type of temperament, it is necessary to make sure that the following qualities are expressed in one way or another:

1. Activity
2. Emotionality
3. Specific characteristics of motor skills.

Each type of temperament can manifest itself in both positive and negative psychological characteristics.

As soon as the child reaches school age and steps on the threshold of the school, he enters a new sphere of life, a new environment. From this period, the content of the child's activities and his attitude to the things and events around him change to a certain extent.

During the junior school period, the child is biologically and psychologically prepared to learn the basics of knowledge. His psyche develops to the point of acquiring knowledge. A child of this age is distinguished from children of other ages by his sharpness of perception, clarity, purity, accuracy, curiosity, trustworthiness, brightness of imagination, strength of memory, clarity of thinking. In a child preparing for school education, attention is relatively long-term and conditionally stable.

The main activity of children of primary school age is reading. A student's attendance at school plays an extremely important role in his psychological development and personality formation. In educational activities, under the guidance of a teacher, he acquires the content of various basic forms of human consciousness and learns to act on the basis of human traditions. In educational activities, the child exercises his will to achieve educational goals. Educational activities require the child to develop speech, attention, memory, imagination and thinking to the required level, and create new conditions for the development of the child's personality. A child who comes to school for the first time enters a new system of psychological relations with those around him. He begins to feel that his life has changed radically, that he has new obligations, not only to go to school every day, but also to obey the requirements of academic activities.

The educational process creates favorable conditions for the development of voluntary, stable, strong, cumulative, distributed, active conscious attention of students. Voluntary conscious attention is included in independent mental work to acquire knowledge and solving problems. Also, its most essential features will be improved. This allows for conscious control. Children's attention develops at the

same time as appropriate social motives for studying and new feelings (feelings of responsibility, responsibility, shame) that appear in them. If it is necessary to organize voluntary concentration in a child of this age, the ability to divide it, overcome the resistance of external stimuli, and consciously control it begins to form.

Adabiyotlar.

1. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.
2. Rahimjon o‘g‘li, A. A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarning Aqliy Taraqqiyotining Rivojlanishida O ‘Yin Rivojlantiruvchi Faoliyat Sifatida. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 207-209.
3. Asqarov, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yosh Davrda Kreativ Tafakkurni Rivojlanishining Ijtimoiy Psixologik Aspektlari. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(6), 882-883.
4. O‘G‘Li, A. A. R. (2022). XOTIRANI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS USULLARI. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali*, 1(6).
5. Kamilova, F. X. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSH DAVRDA MANTIQUIY VA KREATIV TAFAKKUR RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK MEXANIZMLARI VA ASPEKTLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 508-512.
6. o‘g‘li Asqarov, A. R., & Turdimatov, J. (2023). KEKSALIK DAVRIDA XOTIRA JARAYONINING O ‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARINI PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 513-516.

7. o'g'li Asqarov, A. R., & Turdimatova, E. (2023). MANTIQUIY TAFAKKURNI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 482-485.
8. Asqarov, A. R., & Musayev, J. (2023). TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QUVCHI SHAXSI XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAXDIDLAR VA ULARNI BARTARAF QILISHNING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK USULLARI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(15), 254-258.
9. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A., & Baxtiyorovna, M. S. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING INTELLEKTUAL QOBILİYATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA ISTE'DODNING O'RNI. *IQRO*, 3(1), 314-316.
10. Zaylobidin o'g'li, A. I. (2023). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHDAGI O'QUVCHILARDA O'Z-O'ZINI ANGLASHDA IJTIMOIIYLASHUVNI O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(12), 94-98.
11. Ibroximjonovna, N. T. (2023). THE PROBLEM ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS OF CREATIVE THINKING IN EDUCATION. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(4).
12. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A., & Adxam o'g'li, X. A. (2023). INKLYUZIV TA'LIM OLAYOTGAN BOLALARNI TAFAKKUR SOHASINI O'RGANISH.
13. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MANTIQUIY TAFAKKUR RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY PSIXOLOGIK MEXANIZMLARI. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 5(2), 116-119.